

ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTS OF ELECTROMAGNETIC RADIATION ON PLANTS DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract – The population growth of the last decades has created the need to look for new ways to increase the productivity of crops. Knowing this, several studies began to be carried out in order to analyze the influence of electromagnetic radiation on the development of plants. With that in mind, the present work presents an experiment carried out to analyze the influence of the irradiation of an electromagnetic wave of 2.3625 GHz in the development of a corn crop by comparing the growth of this plant exposed to this extra radiation with another that is only exposed to the ambient radiation. The results demonstrate that the plant exposed to the radiation set at a specified frequency has a decrease in root size.

Key-Words: Electromagnetic radiation; Development; Corn; Root;

INTRODUCTION

Due to the exponential growth of the world population over the last centuries, the need for technological advances aimed at agriculture to satisfy the needs has been constant. And this is no different today, with a forecast of 8 billion inhabitants for 2025 and 9 billion for 2050, the need arises to study new more sustainable agriculture techniques, which increase the productivity of crops and use less and less water and energy resources [1].

Over the last few decades, several experiments have been carried out to identify the benefits that the exposure of plants to electromagnetic radiation could cause. Some of these studies presented data that show a relationship between plant growth and the time it is exposed to electromagnetic radiation. According to these researches, keeping the plant exposed to electromagnetic radiation for a certain time results in a chance of increasing the growth capacity of the crop. However, if the test subject gets irradiated for too long, there is a decrease in the germination capacity of the plant [2]. This relationship can be seen in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Relationship between the time of exposure to electromagnetic radiation with plant growth [2].

Besides the time the plant is exposed to electromagnetic radiation, certain studies have shown that the frequencies of these waves can cause different effects on its development. [3]. The Table 1 shows some effects caused by different frequencies.

Frequência	Fenômeno observado
60-100 Hz	Produção de alalina
400, 900, 1900 MHz	Crescimento e alterações bioquímicas
900 MHz	Desenvolvimento da planta
2.4 GHz	Produção de metabólitos secundários
53.6 GHz	Maior germinação

Table 1: Observed phenomena for different frequencies [3]

These relations can be observed in a study carried out in 2005, in which the author of the research, plants *lemna minor* (also known as duckweed) and leaves it exposed to electromagnetic waves of 400 MHz and 900 MHz (both with field 23, 41 and 390 V/m) for two hours daily for 3, 5, 8, 10, 12 and 14 days. At the end of the experiment, it was observed that there was an increase of approximately 15% in the growth capacity of the plant exposed to a wave of 400 MHz, electric field of 23 V/m, exposed for two hours a day over three days. On the other hand, in other cases, it was possible to observe a reduction in the plant's growth capacity [4].

As shown in the research cited above, different frequencies cause different effects on plants. Some other studies carried out more recently, had data that also pointed support to this fact. A work carried out in 2007 presents data regarding the irradiation of an alternating magnetic field of a wave of 50Hz, in these data it is possible to perceive that there was an increase in the yield of the beet roots [5]. Another study carried out in 2021, pointed out a phenomenon that happened in a forest near a village in Turkey in which the vegetation near a radio tower located in this forest was extremely negatively affected by the electromagnetic fields generated in that tower. In this research, as they got closer and closer to the tower, the vegetation was gradually reduced due to the high exposure of the radiation generated by the radio tower [6]. This graphic relationship between the number of plants

present and the distance from the tower can be seen in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Graphic representation of the number of plants with the distance from the tower [6].

Knowing these facts discussed above, the present experiment proposes to analyze the influence of exposure to electromagnetic radiation on the development of corn, observing the positive or negative influences that may occur according to the time in which the corn is exposed to radiation.

DEVELOPMENT

To carry out this experiment, two cultures of *zea mays*, also known as corn corn (QUALITÁ-Alnutri Alimentos Ltda.), were planted in Styrofoam pots filled with soil, as shown in Fig. 3, where one of the cultures was exposed to electromagnetic radiation for two hours a day for five days, while the other culture was exposed only to ambient electromagnetic radiation. The corn used is distributed by the company GPA and its lot is 0000024206.

Figure 3: Cultures of *zea mays*, the top one was considered the "control" and the bottom one the "radiated".

In addition, cultures were watered daily with 25 mL of mineral water (CRYSTAL-Spal Indústria Brasileira de Bebidas S.A.) which, at 25°C, has a pH of 7.49, conductivity of 204 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and evaporation residue at 180°C of 160.70 mg/L. In addition, its composition has 131.77 mg/L of NaHCO_3 , 43.561 mg/L of Na^+ , 4,698 mg/L of Ca^+ , 2,503 mg/L of K^+ , 1,94 mg/L of Cl^- , 1,233 mg/L of Mg^+ , 1 mg/L of F^- , 0,98 mg/L of SO_4^{2-} , 0,68 mg/L of PO_4^{3-} , 0,144 mg/L of Ba, 0,053 mg/L of B, 0,050 mg/L of Sr, 0,035 mg/L of Fe and 0,03 mg/L of NO_3^- .

Figura 4: Água e Milho utilizados.

To carry out the electromagnetic bombardment, a timer was used that has the function of turning a microwave generator on and off, which was set to work for a period of 2 hours a day. This equipment can be seen in Fig.5.

Figure 5: timer used in the experiment.

In addition, for the purpose of also radiating the electromagnetic waves to the ground, a signal generator and a patch-type antenna were used. The system assembled with these devices can be seen in Fig. 6. The signal generator used generates a wave of approximately 2.3625 GHz, as represented in the radiation diagram of Fig.7.

Figure 6: system used to irradiate the soil.

Figure 7: Microwave generator radiation diagram.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experiments were carried out under the following conditions, two separate Styrofoam pots were filled using land from the same source, and within each of them, five seeds were planted in order to increase the chance of successful germination. One of the soil amounts was irradiated for two hours a day over five days, and after that, it was waited another five days for both the irradiated and the control to develop.

During the experiment, it was possible to observe some effects that the electromagnetic radiation radiated on the corn seeds caused after ten days of growth, however, for an experiment to be complete it would be necessary to observe a frequency in the results. For this, the same procedure was performed three times, in the same place with very similar luminosity (measured with the aid of a luxmeter).

After the first ten days, the plants were removed from their land and their growth compared to the control plant could be observed, as shown in Fig. 8 and 9.

Figure 8: Length of plant irradiated with micro-waves in experiment

1

Figure 9: Control plant length in experiment 1

This measurement was carried out with all the seeds of the experiment, comparing the size of the control plants with the irradiated ones, and in this experiment, it can be seen that speaking in terms of average, the roots of the control plants are larger than the irradiated ones, and they presented a better growth. In this case, taking the best developed ones from each pot, a difference of approximately 2 cm can be observed in their roots, where the one without radiation had 28 cm and the plant exposed to radiation approximately 26 cm.

To continue the experiment, the same event was performed again, and after another ten days the results presented in Fig. 10 and 11.

Figure 10: Length of plant irradiated with micro-waves in experiment 2

Figure 11: Control plant length in experiment 2

Again, it is possible to observe a pattern in the terms of the root size of plants without radiation being significantly larger than those with radiation, considering the measured values: 23 cm with radiation and 29 cm without radiation (rounding was used in the measurements since the roots of plants are not perfectly straight and too fragile for us to force them straight).

To guarantee the thesis, another experiment was carried out, using the same patterns previously followed. The results obtained can be seen in Fig. 12 and 13.

Figure 12: Length of plant irradiated with micro-waves in experiment 3

Figure 13: Control plant length in experiment 3

It can be seen that the pattern was maintained in these roots, and although this experiment had the same period of 10 days, the climate was less favorable for the growth of the plant in question (low temperatures), but even so, the growth of the two plants is shown to be with the same equivalence pattern where the plant with radiation has 11 cm of roots, and the one without

radiation has 15 cm, being able to observe the obviously influence in the growth of the plant.

The results obtained made possible to conclude that the electromagnetic waves caused the roots to suffer a negative influence on their growth, but an interesting point to highlight is that despite the delayed development of the roots, their growth as a plant remained on par with the same the control plant.

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